

CREEP BEHAVIOR OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A model is developed to predict the steady-state creep behavior of both aligned and misaligned short fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites. The approach is based on an advanced shear-lag model. The analysis incorporates some unique characteristics of ceramic matrix composites, such as the fiber/matrix interface sliding effect, shear and axial loads carried by the matrix, and the fact that both the fibers and matrix creep at elevated temperatures. Several parameters, such as fiber volume fraction, fiber aspect ratio, sliding factor, coefficient of sliding friction, and the misorientation angle are varied to determine their effect on the creep behavior. Finally, the results from the model are compared with experimental data of a SiC/Al₂O₃ composite.

INTRODUCTION

Several analyses have been reported¹⁻⁶ for modeling the steady-state creep deformation of fiber reinforced composites. Most of these works are concerned with polymer and metal matrix composites. Many analyses assume that there is a perfect bond at the fiber/matrix interface²⁻⁵. However, in ceramic matrix composites, it is often desirable to minimize the chemical bonds at the fiber/matrix interface in order to improve the composite toughness⁷. Thus, sliding will occur along the interface. Next, the fibers are often assumed to be rigid and do not creep^{2,3,6}. Other researchers assume that there is a fiber creeping length where the fiber and matrix are creeping at the same constant rate. Outside of this length, the fiber is assumed to be rigid¹. Also, the existing analyses in the literature often assume that the matrix does not carry the applied load; the function of the matrix is merely for transferring the load to the fibers through its stress relaxation due to creep^{2,4,8}. The purpose of this paper is, therefore, to develop a better understanding of the creep behavior of ceramic matrix composites.

The basic approach used here is based on an advanced shear-lag model⁹. This model assumes that both the fibers and matrix can creep. It also takes into account that there could be a fiber creeping length, over which both the fiber and matrix are creeping at the same rate. Next, it assumes that the matrix is capable of carrying axial loads, as well as shear loads. It also assumes that there is sliding along the fiber/matrix interface. Lastly, different geometrical arrangements for the same volume fraction are taken into account. A SiC whisker reinforced Al₂O₃ composite has been selected as the model system of this study. The creep data of the fiber and matrix are adopted from experimental results^{10,11}.

CREEP LAWS FOR FIBER AND MATRIX

The stress-strain rate relation of the fiber and matrix under uniaxial creep condition is chosen to be the power law, which has been shown to match experimental data very well¹¹, and is given as

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A (\nabla/G)^n \exp(-Q/RT) \quad (1)$$

where A and n are constants, Q is the activation energy, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, G is the shear modulus, $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate and ∇ is the

stress. For any given temperature, the above constants can be combined to give

$$\dot{\epsilon} = (\nabla/C)^n \quad (2)$$

where C and n are constants.

The creep law for a multiaxial state of stress is given as¹²⁻¹⁵

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = (3/2) (\nabla_e/C)^{n-1} (S_{ij}/C) \quad (3)$$

where S_{ij} , the stress deviation tensor, is defined as

$$S_{ij} = \nabla_{ij} - (1/3) \delta_{ij} \nabla_{kk} \quad (4)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, and ∇_e , the effective stress, is given as

$$\nabla_e^2 = (3/2) S_{ij} S_{ij} \quad (5)$$

ANALYSIS-ALIGNED FIBERS

The schematic of a fiber arrangement is shown in Fig. 1. For the analysis of the composite, a unit cell is used, which is the smallest repeating unit of the composite. For a given volume fraction, there are two different possible fiber arrangements: one in which the fibers overlap, and one in which the fibers don't overlap, as shown in Fig. 2. Due to symmetry, it is only necessary to consider half of the unit cell for each model.

Fig. 1 Schematic of an aligned composite system.

Fig. 2 Different models for the same volume fraction.

In both models, it is necessary to know how to handle the matrix in front of the fiber ends. It is assumed here that there is no stress transfer from the matrix to the fiber at the fiber ends, so there will be zero stress in the matrix and fiber there. However, away from the fiber ends, the matrix should be able to carry part of the applied load. Thus, an effective area is defined over which the matrix between fiber ends can carry the load. This area is assumed to vary linearly. Thus, the effective thickness of the matrix in Domain I of Model A is $h+t_{corr}$ where

$$t_{corr} = (t/2) (1-x/g) \quad (6)$$

Here, g is the distance from the beginning of the unit cell to the fiber 1 tip. The matrix thickness for Domain II of Model B is given as $h+t/2+t_{corr}$, where

$$t_{\text{corr}} = (t/2)(x - L_f) / (L/2 - L_f) \quad (7)$$

L_f is the length of a fiber in the unit cell, and L is the length of the unit cell.

In Model A, the equilibrium equations for Domain I are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\tau_2}{dx} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right) + \tau_2 &= 0 \\ \frac{d\tau_m}{dx} t_m + \frac{dt_m}{dx} \tau_m - \tau_2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $t_m = h + t_{\text{corr}}$. Similar equations can be written for Domain II. The equations for Domain I of Model B are the same as those of Domain I of Model A, except that the matrix thickness is constant in Model B. The fourth order Runge-Kutta method¹⁶ is chosen to solve the above equations.

SHEAR STRESS AT THE FIBER/MATRIX INTERFACE

The bond between the fiber and matrix in ceramic matrix composites is generally not a chemical one, but more frictional in nature. Therefore, sliding can occur along the interface. Two different methods of determining the shear stress at the fiber/matrix interface have been used. The first method¹⁷ is based on a sliding factor. The shearing of the matrix is caused from the difference in velocities between the matrix and the fiber/matrix interface:

$$\dot{\gamma} = (2/h)(\dot{u}_m - \dot{u}_f) \quad (9)$$

where $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear strain rate, \dot{u}_m is the velocity of the matrix, and \dot{u}_f is the velocity of the fiber. The sliding of the fiber/matrix interface is given as

$$\dot{u}_i = \dot{u}_f + \dot{u}_s \quad (10)$$

Here it is assumed that \dot{u}_s , the sliding velocity, is¹

$$\dot{u}_s = \eta (\dot{u}_m - \dot{u}_f) \quad (11)$$

where η is the sliding factor and $0 < \eta < 1$. To determine the shear stress - shear strain rate dependence, we follow the method used by McLean⁶ and set $\dot{\gamma}_m = 2\dot{\tau}$ and set $\dot{\epsilon}_m = 0.5\dot{\gamma}$. Thus the shear stress, τ , becomes

$$\tau = (C_m/2) \left((1-\eta)/h (\dot{u}_m - \dot{u}_f) \right)^{1/n_m} \quad (12)$$

The second method is based on the friction at the interface. The relationship between the shear stress, τ , and the normal pressure, P , at the fiber/matrix interface is¹⁸

$$\tau = -\mu P \quad (13)$$

where μ is the coefficient of sliding friction.

Due to the presence of the fiber, the matrix will not creep as much in the radial direction as it would if the fiber were absent, and due to the matrix, the fiber will creep more in the radial direction than it would if the matrix was absent. Due to the fact that the matrix wants to creep more than the fiber will let it, a pressure, P , is built up at the fiber/matrix interface. Thus, P has to be solved for such that the creep rates of the fiber and matrix in the radial direction are equal. Noting that P is negative with respect to the fiber, and acts as a positive pressure on the matrix, the equality of strain rates gives P implicitly as

$$\begin{aligned} (\dot{\gamma}_f^2 + P^2 - \dot{\gamma}_f P + 3(\mu P)^2)^{(\eta_f - 1)/2} \left[-\frac{1}{3}\dot{\gamma}_f + \frac{2}{3}P \right] / (C_f)^{\eta_f} = \\ (\dot{\gamma}_m^2 + P^2 + \dot{\gamma}_m P + 3(\mu P)^2)^{(\eta_m - 1)/2} \left[-\frac{1}{3}\dot{\gamma}_m - \frac{2}{3}P \right] / (C_m)^{\eta_m} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

FIBER CREEPING LENGTH

Under a given loading situation, material properties, and geometric parameters, there exists the possibility of a fiber creeping length, defined here as the length over which the fiber and matrix are creeping at the same (but not necessarily constant) rate. If there is a fiber creeping length, and if it extends into Domain II of Model A, then a new set of governing equations is needed for Domain II in the region where fiber 2 and the matrix are creeping at the same rate, and fiber 1 is creeping at a different rate. The governing equations are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\sigma_s}{dx} (h + t/2) + \tau_i &= 0 \\ \frac{d\tau_i}{dx} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right) - \tau_i &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where the stress on the fiber 2/matrix system is

$$\sigma_s = F_s / (h + t/2) \quad (16)$$

where F_s is the force acting on this system.

ANALYSIS-MISALIGNED FIBERS

The stresses acting on a unit cell of a misaligned composite are shown in Fig. 3.

The stresses shown are obtained from the applied stress by a transformation through the angle θ . The problem is now broken into 3 parts: the unit cell subjected to the 3 applied stresses separately. The case with the normal stress σ_x applied along the axis of the fibers is solved the same way as in the aligned case. For the problem with an applied shear stress τ_{xy} , a constant state of shear stress is assumed inside the unit cell. The case of the normal stress σ_y being applied perpendicular to the fibers is solved using a "spring" model, in which a constant strain rate of the unit cell in the y-direction is assumed.

Fig. 3 Stresses on a misaligned unit cell.

The three strain rates, $\dot{\epsilon}_x$, $\dot{\epsilon}_y$, and $\dot{\epsilon}_{xy}$ are obtained from the multiaxial creep law using the three stresses obtained above. These strain rates are averaged throughout the unit cell, and the strain rate of the composite is given as¹⁹

$$\dot{\epsilon}_c = \dot{\epsilon}_{x,ave} (\cos^2 \theta) + \dot{\epsilon}_{y,ave} (\sin^2 \theta) - 2 \dot{\epsilon}_{xy,ave} (\sin \theta \cos \theta) \quad (17)$$

For composites with fibers at different angles, the average creep rate of the composite depends on the fiber orientation distribution, and is given by²⁰

$$\dot{\epsilon}_c = \int_0^{\pi/2} n(\theta) \dot{\epsilon}_c(\theta) d\theta \quad (18)$$

where $n(\theta)$ is the probability density function of fiber orientation.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES

There has been a wide range of data reported for the creep properties of SiC and

Al₂O₃^{10,11,21-24}. The composite creep data that is being compared with the analysis comes from Porter and Chokshi¹⁰. The alumina they used in the composite exhibited a stress exponent (n_m) of 1.6, and a value of 41,295 MPa-s^{1/n_m} for C_m was obtained from a graph of stress vs. strain rate for the alumina. The SiC/Al₂O₃ composite showed a stress exponent of 5.2, which suggests that the fiber should have a stress exponent greater than this. Carter and Davis¹¹ reported a stress exponent of 5.7 for SiC. This value was used for n_f here, and a value of 2428 MPa-s^{1/n_f} for C_f was calculated from the creep data of the same SiC.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values of several parameters were varied to show their effect on the creep rate. First, as shown in Fig. 4, it is seen that for a sliding factor of about 0.4 or less, the creep rate does not vary that much, but the creep rate is very sensitive to high values of the sliding factor¹⁷. Next, Fig. 5 shows that as the angle of misorientation increases, so does the creep rate, up to about 70°. After this point, the creep rate decreases by a small amount, but stays relatively constant. Also, Model A predicts a lower creep rate than Model B up until 50°, and after this it has a slightly higher strain rate than Model B. Lastly, the results from the analysis with the shear stress related to the coefficient of sliding friction are shown with experimental data in Fig. 6. Model A with aligned fibers predicts a lower creep rate than Model B with aligned fibers, and has a slope of 2.6 compared with 2.2 for Model B. The lines for the random fibers for both models fall almost exactly on top of each other, the slope for Model A being 1.8, and 1.7 for Model B. The slope for the experimental data is 5.2. There are two main reasons why the slopes of the calculated lines don't match the experimental results, besides the uncertainty of the material properties to use. First, this analysis assumes that the composite is under pure tension, whereas the experimental data are from a bending test, in which both tension and compression are present. Also, this work assumes that the matrix and fibers are perfect and have no damage, and thus neglects matrix cracking. With this cracking, the matrix cannot carry as much of the load, thus forcing the fibers to carry a greater share of the load. Therefore, the stress exponent of the composite would be closer to that of the fiber, as has been shown in the experimental data.

CONCLUSIONS

An analysis based on an advanced shear-lag model has been performed of the creep behavior of short fiber reinforced ceramic composites. The effects on the creep rate of the fiber volume fraction, fiber aspect ratio, sliding factor, coefficient of sliding friction, and the misorientation angle have been shown. The results are also shown with experimental data.

Fig. 4 The effect of the sliding factor on the composite creep rate; $V_f = 25\%$, $L/D = 30$, $\tau_{app} = 100$ MPa.

Fig. 5 The effect of the fiber misorientation angle on the composite creep rate; $V_f = 25\%$, $L/D = 30$, $\mu = 5.0$, $\sigma_{app} = 100$ MPa.

Fig. 6 Comparison of Models A and B with experimental data; $V_f = 20\%$, $L/D = 30$, $\mu = 5.0$.

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